

**INGLIZ TILIDA EKZOTIK LEKSIKANING TARJIBIY XUSUSIYATLARI
(FRANSUZ,ISPAN,YAPON,XITOIY VA H.K MISOLIDA)**

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilidagi ekzotik so‘zlar uning mavzuviy guruhlari, qaysi tildan olinganligi, ularning nima ma‘no anglatishi haqida va boshqa ko‘plab qiziqarli ma‘lumotlarga ega bo‘lasiz.

Kalit so‘zlar: *sombrera, trombone, ekzotik so‘zlar, peso, wazir, Kaaba*

Аннотация. В этой статье вы получите информацию об экзотических английских словах, их тематических группах, из какого языка они происходят, что означают и много другой интересной информации.

Ключевые слова: *сомбрера, тромбон, экзотические слова, песо, везир, Кааба.*

Abstract. In this article, you will get information about exotic English words, their thematic groups, which language they come from, what they mean, and a lot of other interesting information.

Keywords: *sombrera, trombone, exotic words, peso, wazir, Kaaba*

Dunyoda hech bir til yo‘qki uning lo‘g‘at tarkibi sof, faqat o‘sha tildagi so‘zlardan iborat bo‘lsa. Barcha tillar uchun umumiy xususiyat hisoblangan ushbu jihat sababini turlicha tushunishimiz mumkin. Yillar davomida tillarning, bevosita uning foydalanuvchilari bo‘lgan xalqlarning va davlatlarning tarixan uzoq vaqtlardan beri bir birlari bilan uzviy xolda olib borayotgan ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, madaniy, ma‘rifiy, siyosiy aloqalari ,do‘stona munosabatlari kerak bo‘lsa turli davrlardagi urushlar va katta-katta hududlarning egallanib olishi, tilshunoslikdagi substrat va superstrat atamalari bilan bog‘liq jarayonlar ta‘sirida xar bir tilda o‘zga tildan kirgan turli xil so‘zlar uchrashi ingliz tiliga ham begona emas. Til jamiyat uning faol a‘zosi bo‘lgan inson bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgani sabab insoniyat tarixida tillarda lo‘g‘at tarkibi boyib borishi bir tomondan til tarixini davrlashtirish imkonini bersa boshqa tomondan shu tilning “umr”ini, o‘tmishini belgilab beradi. Ingliz tili xalqaro tan olingan dunyo tillaridan biri bo‘lgani bois va Buyuk Britaniya qirolligi mustamlakalari ko‘pligi va sarhadlari kengligi shunigdek mustamlaka davrlarining uzoqligi va shu sababdan turli qit‘alardagi turli davlatlar va ularning tillaridagi ularning madaniyati turmushi hayot tarziga xos bo‘lgan ayrim so‘zlarning ingliz tiliga kirib kelganini ko‘rishimiz mumkin. Bunday so‘zlarni qabul qilish sababi esa ingliz tilida unga ekvivalent, ma‘nodosh yoki unga muqobil variantdagi so‘zning yo‘q ekanligi yoki shu so‘z o‘sha millat uchungina xosligi, u orqali shu millat yoki millat tili, davlat (masalan: ingliz tilidagi quyidagi “sari” so‘zini eshitishimiz bilan hind tili, hind xalqi yoki Hindiston davlati yodimizga kelsa, “samurai” so‘zi bizga Yapon tili, millati va davlatini “sombrera” so‘zi esa bizga Meksika xalqi, davlati va ispan tilini, “yuan” so‘zi orqali esa ko‘p sonli Xitoy xalqi, tili, davlatini) ko‘z oldimizga gavdalantiradi. Barcha tillarda bo‘lgani singari ingliz tilida ham turli til birliklari mavjud. Yuqorida biz namuna sifatida keltirgan so‘zlar esa ekzotik til birliklari deb nomlanadi. Bunday so‘zlarning ingliz tili lo‘g‘at tarkibida ko‘p ekanligini tushunamiz. Shunga ko‘ra hozirgi ingliz tili lo‘g‘at boyligidagi mavjud o‘shlashma so‘zlardan ekzotik so‘zlarning ajratib oldik va ularni quyidagi mavzuviy guruhlarga bo‘lib chiqdik.

1) Art-San‘at sohasiga oid bo‘lgan ekzotik so‘zlar: Trombone -(italyancha)-is a brass musical instrument with a sliding bar that changes the pitch of the notes, Bagpipes-(shotlandcha) -

is a wind instrument consisting of a reed melody pipe and from one to five drones with air supplied continuously either by a bag with valve-stopped mouth tube or by bellows, Bhangra-(panjobcha)- is popular dance music originating chiefly in the Punjabi community in Britain ,flugelhorn-(nemischa)-is a valved brass instrument resembling a cornet but having a larger bore ,Kabuki-(yaponcha)-is traditional Japanese popular drama performed with highly stylized singing and dancing

2) A unit of monetary and measurements- pul va o'lichov birliklari nomlariga oid bo'lgan ekzotik so'zlar: Bushel-(fransuzcha)-is British imperial and dry measure, Dollar-(nemischa)-is a unit of currency or money, Dinar-(arabcha)-monetary unit used in several Middle Eastern countries, Drechma-(lotincha)-is silver coin of ancient Greece, Gallon-(fransuzcha)-is a unit of measurement for volume, commonly used in the United States and the United Kingdom for liquids, Peso-(ispancha)-is the monetary unit of several countries in the Americas and the Philippines.

3) Medicine-tibbiyot sohasiga oid bo'lgan ekzotik so'zlar

Accupuncture -(xitoycha)-is a form of alternative medicine in China in which thin needles are inserted into the body, Shiatsu-(yaponcha)-is a Japanese finger pressure technique used primarily for musculoskeletal (neck, shoulder) and psychological (depression, stress, anxiety) problems.

4) Religious- Diniy mavzuga oid ekzotik so'zlar:

Qiblah-(arabcha)-is the direction towards the Kaaba in the Sacred Mosque in Mecca, which is used by Muslims, Ramadan-(arabcha)-is the most sacred month of the year in Islamic culture, The Rig Veda-(hindcha)-s an ancient Indian collection of Vedic Sanskrit hymns, Talmud-(yahudiy)-s a large collection of writings, containing a full account of the civil and religious laws of the Jews, Unitarian-(lotincha)- member of an organisation that follows, any of several theologies referred to as Unitarianism.

5) Building-Bino va uy bilan bog'liq bo'lgan ekzotik so'zlar:

Yurt-(ruscha)-is a tentlike dwelling of the Mongol and Turkic peoples of central Asia, Casino-(italyancha)-is a building or room used for social amusements, Cottage-(inglizcha)-s a modest dwelling, typically in a rural, or semi-rural location, Crematorium-(lotincha)-a building where dead people's bodies are burned, The Dail-(irlandcha)-is "Deptment of Aging and Independent Living"., Igloo-(amerika hindulari tilida)-known as a snow house or snow hut, is a type of shelter built.

6) Social class- ijtimoiy toifa, guruhga oid bo'lgan ekzotik leksika:

Mafia-(italyancha)-is a secret criminal society of Sicily or Italy, Casta-(iberiyancha)-is a term which means "lineage" in Spanish and Portuguese and has historically been used as a racial and social identifier, Dervish-(turkcha)-is a member of a Muslim religious.

7) Social status- Turli ijtimoiy maqomni ifodalovchi ekzotik so'zlar:

Courier-(fransuzcha)-a person or company that takes messages, letters, or parcels from one person or place to another, cowboy-(Amerika ingliz tili)-a man who herds and tends cattle, performing much of his work on horseback, Fakir-(arabcha)-a member of any Islamic religious order, Gladiator-(italyancha)-was an armed combatant, Hakim-(arabcha)-a Muslim judge, ruler, or administrator.

8) Social position- Ijtimoiy lavozim, mansabga ega bo'lgan ekzotik leksika:

Sarpanch-(sanskritcha)-head of the five decision-makers of the gram panchayat of the village, Senator-(amerika ingliz tili)-is a person who works in the government, Sheriff-(anglo-saks

tili)-is generally an elected county official, Wazir yoki vizier-(arabcha)-is a high-ranking political advisor or minister.

9. Social-Ijtmoyiy munosabatlar va undagi hodisalar bilan bog‘liq ekzotik leksika:

Tete a tete-(fransuzcha)-means "head to head., Aka-(o‘zbekcha)-, Bumbag-(Amerika ingliz tili)-a small bag attached to a long strap that you fasten around your waist, used for carrying money, keys, Clan-(shotlandcha)-is an extended family, Lobola-Zulu(Afrika xalqlari tili)- an African custom by which a bridegroom's family makes a payment in cattle or cash to the bride's family shortly before the marriage.

10. Military-Xarbiy sohaga oid bo‘lgan ekzotik so‘zlar:

Admiral-(qadimgi ingliz tili)-a naval commissioned officer with a rank above that of captain, Garda-(irlandcha)-a police officer in the Republic of Ireland., Gendarme-(qadimgi fransuzcha,)- member of a body of soldiers especially in France serving as an armed police force for the maintenance of public order, Gurkha -(nepalcha)-a member of a Hindu people, descended from Brahmins and Rajputs.

11. Science-Ilm fan bilan bog‘liq ekzotik so‘zlar:

Taoism-(xitoycha)-is a diverse tradition indigenous to China, yogo-(sanskritcha)-uniting the body and the mind with the soul.

12. Ethnic-Turli kichik etnik-xalqlar bilan bog‘liq ekzotik so‘zlar:

Eskima-(fransuzcha)-is related [Indigenous peoples](#), Gullah-(Angolcha)a member of a group of Black people inhabiting the sea islands-, "Hausa"-Afrika xalqlaridan, Inuit-Meksika hindu xalqlaridan, Koori-Avstraliyada yashovchi xalq.

13. Drink-Ichimlik nomlari bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan ekzotik so‘zlar:

"Liebfraumilch"-nemischa, "Liquor"-Amerika ingliz tili, "Marsala"-italyancha, "Muscadet"-fransuzcha, "Raki"-turkcha.

14. Fauna-Hayvonat olamiga oid bo‘lgan ekzotik so‘zlar:

"Tsetse fly"-eski ingliz tili-, "Wasabia"-yaponcha, "kangaroo"-Avstraliya aboragenlari tili, "Baboon"-fransuzcha, "Chimpanze"-fransuzcha.

15. Clothes-Kiyim kechak bilan bogliq ekzotik so‘zlar:

"Cordorey"-fransuzcha, "Dashhund"-nemischa, "Dhoti" -hindcha, "Gharara"-forscha, "Kikoi"-Sharqiy afrika tili.

16. Games and sport-O‘yin va sport nomlari bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan ekzotik leksika:

"Korfbal"-nederlandcha, "Kungfu"-xitoycha, "Matador"-ispancha, "Origami"-yaponcha, "Rodeo"-ispancha, "Ping Pong"-xitoycha, "Shotakan"-yaponcha, "Sumo"-yaponcha.

17. Place-mashxur joy va makon bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan ekzotik so‘zlar:

"Woop-woop"-Avstraliya mahalliy tilida, "Fleet street"-inglizcha, "Piazzat"-italyancha, "Harley street"-inglizcha, "Hollywood"-Amerika ingliz tili.

18. Cities-Shaxar nomlari bilan bog‘liq ekzotik leksika:

Westminister-inglizcha, Bollywood-hindcha, Gorgan-forscha, Gujarat-hindcha.

19. Holiday-Bayram nomlari bilan bog‘liq ekzotik leksika:

Carnival-italyancha, Diwali-hindcha, Eid-arabcha, Fiesta-ispancha, Halloween-inglizcha, Kwanzaa-Afrika ingliz tili.

20. Household items - Uy ro‘zg‘or anjomlariga oid ekzotik so‘zlar: Samovar-ruscha,

Tomahawk-Amerika hindulari tili, Dirk- kelib chiqishi noma‘lum, Doona-Avstraliya ingliz tili, Duvet-fransuzcha.

21. Food-Oziq ovqat va taom nomlari bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan ekzotik so‘zlar:
Edam-nederlandcha, Enchilada-ispansha, Falafel-arabcha, Fondue-fransuzcha, Gazpacho-ispansha, Ghee-sanskritcha, Goulash -vengercha.
22. Administrative- Davlat va davlat boshqaruviga oid bo‘lgan ekzotik so‘zlar:
Sheikh-arabcha, Suffragette-lotinch, Taluk-forscha, Kaiser-nemischa, Field marshal-qadimgi nemis tili.
23. Flora-O‘simlik olamiga oid ekzotik so‘zlar:
Guava-ispansha, Ikebane yaponcha, Lychee-xitoycha, Matoke-Luganda tili (Uganda), Rattan-malaycha.
24. Ceremony- turli xil marosim rasm rusmlar bilan bog‘liq ekzotik leksika:
Inauguration-lotinch, jubilee-fransuzcha, Tangi-Maori.
25. Footwear- Oyoq kiyim bilan bog‘liq ekzotik so‘zlar:
Desert boot-qadimgi inglizcha, Moccasin-shotlandcha, Huarache-Amerika hindular tilida. Language-
26. Til va til bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan ekzotik so‘zlar:
Jiu jitsu-yaponcha, Kanji-yaponcha (yozuvi nomi).
27. Literature-Adabiyot va xalq og‘zaki ijodi bilan bog‘liq ekzotik so‘zlar:
Don Juan-ispansha, Helene-grekcha, Odyssey-lotinch.
28. Cloth-Mato nomlari bilan bog‘liq ekzotik so‘zlar:
Gingham-niderlandcha, Toga-italyancha, Khaki-urdu tilida.
29. Head cloth- Bosh kiyim bilan bog‘liq ekzotik so‘zlar:
Topi (tapee)-Inglizcha, Toque-fransuzcha.
30. Title - Turli unvonlar nomlari bilan bog‘liq ekzotik so‘zlar”
Sherif-arabcha, Sultan-arabcha, Taoiseach-irlandcha, Titan-grekcha.
31. City, town- Dunyoga tanilgan shaharlar nomlariga oid ekzotik so‘zlar:
Bollywood-hindcha, Gorgan-forcha, Gujarat-hindcha, Mecca-arabcha.
32. Historical person-Tarixiy va dunyoviy shaxs nomlari ekzotik so‘zlar:
Genghiskhan-turkiycha, Houdini-Amerika ingliz tilisi, Goliath-lotinch.
33. Natural phenomenon- Tabiatga aloqador voqeyliklarga oid ekzotik so‘zlar:
Elnino-ispansha, Fohn-lotinch, Gondwano-sanskritcha.
34. Awards-Turli nomdagi mukofot nomlariga oid ekzotik so‘zlar:
Oscar-irlandcha, Pulitzer Prize-inglizcha, Nobel Prize-inglizcha.
35. Vehicle- Tarnsport vositasi nomlari bilan bog‘liq ekzotik so‘zlar:
Cruiser-niderlandcha, Dhow-hindcha, Limousine-fransuzcha.
36. Education-Ta’lim sohasiga oid ekzotik so‘zlar:” Freshman”-inglizcha:, Sophomore”:-lotinch.
37. Cosmetics - Kosmetika mahsulotlari nomlari so‘z:
Kajal-hindcha,

Yuqorida mavzuviy guruhlariga ajratilgan ekzotik so‘zlardan shuni xulosa qilishimiz mumkinki ingliz tili juda ham ko‘p tillardan turli mavzuga doir ekzotik so‘zlarni qabul qilgan. Agar ingliz tilini bir “taom” sifatida qaraydigan bo‘lsak uni eng ko‘p “masalliq”li “taom” deya ta’rif etishimiz mumkin. Xulosa o‘rnida shuni aytishimiz mumkinki ingliz tili xalqaro dunyo tillaridan biri bo‘lishi uning “sof’lik darajasi tushib ketayotganligiga sabab bo‘lishi bilan

izohlansa, lekin uning til sifatida taraqqiy etishi, boyishi ayni shunday til birliklari bilan sodir bo‘lishini xech ham inkor eta olmaymiz.

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